

Stig2Health: Stigma-directed services to improve ‘linkage to care’ for people living with HIV in rural Tanzania: study protocol for a nested pre-post implementation study within the Kilombero and Ulanga Antiretroviral Cohort

HIV Stigma Scale (adapted ‘Berger et al 2001’ Scale)

Kindly provided by Prof. Sylvia Kaaya, Permission to publish received 28.01.2022

DATE _____	HCW NAME _____
NAME OF PATIENT _____	NACP NUMBER _____

“NITAKUULIZA MASWALI MACHACHE ILI KUPATA MAWAZO YAKO KUHUSU KUISHI NA VVU. TAFADHALI ONYESHA NI KWA KIASI GANI UNAKUBALIANA AU HUKUBALIANI NA KILA KAULI IFUATAYO”

		Nakataa kabisa	Nakataa	Sikubali wala sikatai	Nakubali	Nakubali kabisa	N/A
<i>HSD 1</i>	NAJIHISI KUJILAUMU KWA KUWA NA VVU I I FEEL GUILTY BECAUSE I HAVE HIV	5	4	3	2	1	
<i>HSD 2</i>	NAJISIKIA AIBU KWA SABABU NINA VVU I FEEL ASHAMED BECAUSE I HAVE HIV	5	4	3	2	1	
IN THE NEXT 5 QUESTIONS, KINDLY ANSWER IF YOU TOLD OTHER PEOPLE ABOUT YOUR HIV STATUS OR YOU THINK THAT OTHERS KNOW YOU HAVE HIV. IF THE QUESTION REFERS TO SOMETHING THAT HAS NOT ACTUALLY HAPPENED TO YOU, PLEASE ANSWER ("NOT APPLICABLE N/A")							
<i>HSD 3</i>	WATU BADO WANANIKUMBATIA PAMOJA NA KWAMBA WANAJUA KUWA NINA VVU PEOPLE STILL HUG ME DESPITE KNOWING I HAVE HIV [WEKA N/A IKIWA HAJAWAHI KUMSHIRIKISHA MTU HALI YAKE YA MAAMBUKIZI] ANSWER N/A IF THE CLIENT/PATIENT HAS NOT TOLD ANYONE ABOUT THEIR HIV STATUS	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
<i>HSD 4</i>	WATU NINAO WAJALI WANANIPIGIA SIMU MARA KWA MARA BAADA YA KUJUA NINAISHI NA VVU. PEOPLE I CARE ABOUT STILL CALL ME FROM TIME TO TIME DESPITE KNOWING THAT I LIVE WITH HIV [WEKA N/A IKIWA HAJAWAHI KUMSHIRIKISHA MTU HALI YAKE YA MAAMBUKIZI] ANSWER N/A IF THE CLIENT/PATIENT HAS NOT TOLD ANYONE ABOUT THEIR HIV STATUS	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
<i>HSD 5</i>	WATU BADO WANAFURAHIA KUTUMIA MUDA WAO NA MIMI INGAWAJE WANAJUA NINA VVU DESPITE KNOWING I HAVE HIV, PEOPLE ARE STILL HAPPY TO SPEND THEIR TIME WITH ME	1	2	3	4	5	N/A

	[WEKA N/A IKIWA HAJAWAHI KUMSHIRIKISHA MTU HALI YAKE YA MAAMBUKIZI] ANSWER N/A IF THE CLIENT/PATIENT HAS NOT TOLD ANYONE ABOUT THEIR HIV STATUS						
<i>HSD 6</i>	WATU WANAKWEPA KUWA NAMI KWA SABABU NINA VVU PEOPLE AVOID BEING WITH ME BECAUSE I HAVE HIV [WEKA N/A IKIWA HAJAWAHI KUMSHIRIKISHA MTU HALI YAKE YA MAAMBUKIZI] ANSWER N/A IF THE CLIENT/PATIENT HAS NOT TOLD ANYONE ABOUT THEIR HIV STATUS	5	4	3	2	1	N/A
<i>HSD 7</i>	WATU WANAKUBALI NIKICHEZA NA WATOTO WAO INGAWAJE WANAJUA NINA VVU PEOPLE LET ME PLAY WITH THEIR CHILDREN EVEN THOUGH THEY KNOW I HAVE HIV [WEKA N/A IKIWA HAJAWAHI KUMSHIRIKISHA MTU HALI YAKE YA MAAMBUKIZI] ANSWER N/A IF THE CLIENT/PATIENT HAS NOT TOLD ANYONE ABOUT THEIR HIV STATUS	1	2	3	4	5	N/A
ADD COLUMNS		+	+	+	+		

TOTAL SCORE (2-35 points)	
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